

TELEMEDICINE

A Key to Improve Healthcare Delivery in Remote Areas in Africa

Written by

Muoka Chibuzor Gospel

About the Author

Muoka Chibuzor Gospel hails from Umudioka town, Dunukofia local government area (LGA) in Anambra state, Nigeria. He was born in 1994 to the family of Mr. and Mrs. Uzordinma Muoka. He is an entrepreneur, undergraduate medical researcher, prolific writer, and blogger.

He holds a Bachelor's degree in Biochemistry 2:1 (2011-2015) from Abia State University and is currently a Clinical Student at Abia State University, College of Medicine and Health Sciences, Aba - Nigeria.

He has written several articles in various areas of life, many of which were published online and have earned accolades, rewards, and certifications.

In 2017, his NYSC essay submission to the Bible Society of Nigeria (BSN), which was centred on the "INCORRUPTIBLE JUDICIARY AS A CATALYST FOR AN EQUITABLE AND PROGRESSIVE SOCIETY" made it to the best six nationwide.

In 2019, his essay on "THE MENANCE - CHILD ABUSE" submitted to Abia State University Medical Students Association (ABSUMSA) was the best in the entire faculty.

He desires to continuously be involved in research and creative writings, so as to create positive impacts that contribute to the finding of lasting solutions that pacify the enormous problems of mankind, for a better tomorrow and a peaceful co-existence.

He also has serious commitments in lighting electronics, as he has devoted some of his spare time to learning and repairing lighting gadgets such as rechargeable lamps. This led to the Muokagram initiative (www.muokagram.com), which is geared towards helping to lift African households from the devastating impacts of poor power supply.

Hobbies: Reading, Writing, Blogging, Music, Drawing/Painting, Graphics designing, and Electronics repair. Interests: Academics, Health Care, Pharmaceuticals, Lighting Electronics, Politics, Religion.

Muoka Chibuzor Gospel
Email: muokac@yahoo.com
Tel: 07066999820

15/ Nov/2020

Copyright © 2020 Muoka Chibuzor G. This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I (the Author) wish to acknowledge specially the “**Doctors without Borders**” humanitarian organization; because their work in Africa truly inspired me, and also some of the pictures used in this paper were adapted from their media coverage. This work would not have been possible if the **Nigerian Medical Students Association** (NIMSA) had not called for papers on Telemedicine (the author is grateful to NIMSA); the contributions of Nurse Chimamaka are highly appreciated. The prayers, guidance and support of my parents, siblings, and LT. Professor Ifeoma Nweke cannot be overemphasized.

May God bless them all.

ABSTRACT

The world is fast evolving, and no part is to be left behind. Not even the most remote places in Africa. Healthcare delivery has been a huge challenge to Africa as whole, but the advent of Telemedicine seeks to salvage the poor healthcare condition and bring hope to the hopeless, irrespective of where the homes of patients are located. Using ICT, telemedicine bridges the gap between doctors in remote areas and specialists in other parts of the world. It seeks to bring treatment plans to the doorsteps of remote areas dwellers, to help ensure that patients are not forced to travel long distances in search of healthcare. However, the beauty of telemedicine has been attacked by various circumstances that include poor government policies, low physician density, computer illiteracy, no internet etc. Several measures are to be adopted and implemented if telemedicine is to be of great relevance in Africa. Once they are activated, telemedicine is bound to revolutionize the health sector, of which would bring about increase in life expectancy amid native Africans.

Key words: *Telemedicine, Healthcare, Remote, Africa, Internet.*

Citation: Chibuzor, Muoka G O S P E L. “*TELEMEDICINE: A Key to Improve Healthcare Delivery in Remote Areas in Africa.*” Academia.edu, 2020.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8437272

TELEMEDICINE: A Key to Improve Healthcare Delivery in Remote Areas in Africa

Once upon a time, there was a man by the name Dr Amadi. He was a Nigerian general practitioner and a volunteer of a dedicated humanitarian organization. He embarked on a humanitarian mission with a team of healthcare workers to Aweil, a town located in the remote (interior) areas of South Sudan. During the medical outreach in Aweil, a six months pregnant woman who was extremely short of breath came to the short-staffed healthcare clinic with her husband. She needed oxygen and they needed to help her right away. An ultrasound examination (echocardiogram) of her heart and lungs was carried out, and they suspected some abnormalities in her heart scan result.

But what can they do? Since none of them was a cardiologists. On second thought, **Telemedicine** which literally means “*healing at a distance*” was the only option. Dr Amadi immediately sent the patient history and ultrasound clips using an internet-enabled laptop to a cardiologist in the United Kingdom (UK). A few hours later the cardiologist diagnosed the woman of having a severe heart valve disease condition called “mitral stenosis”.

The cardiologist further contacted an anaesthesiologist and obstetrician who helped to make a treatment plan. The specialists recommended that they should carry out an elective caesarean section to deliver the baby, and then a tubal ligation to prevent the woman from future conceptions because of her bad heart condition, emphasizing that a future pregnancy would endanger her life. They further instructed that the woman should be made to understand because it was a hard decision for a Sudanese woman of childbearing age to make. At this juncture, Dr Amadi came to appreciate the unparalleled beauty of Telemedicine and how it prevents professional isolation. With the help of the specialists from a distance, he and his team had the confidence to proffer to the woman the specialist’s recommendations, of which saved her life and the life of her baby boy.

To foresee the future, one must always understand the past; if one doesn't know where he is coming from, how then will he know where he is going? The rise of telemedicine dates back to the period when leper patients were instructed to ring bells to warn people not to come close to them, because of the infectious nature of the disease. Other simple devices like flags and signs were also employed. In the 19th century, the telephone was invented by Alexander Graham Bell, and in the 20th century the radio, television, and internet came into existence. The telephone became a diagnostic tool when it was used to diagnose a child with Croup (laryngotracheobronchitis) an upper airway infection that blocks breathing, characterized by a barking cough. In the 21st century, as more sophisticated inventions came to light, the field of medicine could not help it, but fall head over heels in love with technological advancements, embracing it the more. Currently, the past attempts to transmit health information would surely appear crude and laughable, because of the sophisticated technologies now at one's disposal. A lot of these technological growths have long been ongoing in the Western world, while the African continent is just awakening from slumber. Irrespective of the slow pace, the will of Africans to stir the uncharted waters of telemedicine and embrace its ingenuity, is a welcomed development.

Telemedicine as a hybrid of technology and medicine has been defined in several ways by various scholars. One of the most hilarious descriptions was by Times Magazine who called telemedicine *"the art of healing by wire."* The numerous definitions have been due to the dynamic nature of telemedicine. However, according to the World Health Organization (WHO), *"Telemedicine is the delivery of health care services, where distance is a critical factor, by all health care professionals using information and communication technologies for the exchange of valid information for the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of disease and injuries, research and evaluation, and for the continuing education*

of health care providers, all in the interests of advancing the health of individuals and their communities.” In essence, telemedicine is the use of electronic communications and software to monitor and treat patients in place of an inpatient visit. It provides clinical support with multiple applications in pathology, dermatology, cardiology, and other medical specialities. It overcomes geographical barriers, uses various types of Information and Communications Technology (ICT), and improves patient health outcome. There are two models of telemedicine: In one type of telemedicine called the **Store-and-Forward telemedicine**, a doctor can upload and share patient files which are analyzed by medical specialists in other parts of the world, and then they share their feedback which helps in the diagnosis and patient treatment. The other type of telemedicine is the **Real-Time telemedicine**, where doctors can discuss patient cases with specialists all over the world in live, real-time meetings via Televideoconsultations. The specialist can also speak with the patient as if it is a face-to-face consultation, and even ask the general practitioner who is with the patient to examine the patient on their behalf. In both models, the use of electricity, internet, and ICT is vital.

Several research studies have found telemedicine to be an effective alternative and often satisfying for patients and providers, while acknowledging that it has a suboptimal contribution in the treatment of patients with chronic illnesses e.g., cancer, epilepsy, diabetes mellitus, that require hospital admission. Thus, physical contact with healthcare professionals is still needed because there is a limit to how far a remote physician can go in illness treatment. Telemedicine proponents have sold it as a solution for patients in remote areas. Equally important to mention is the fact that telemedicine served to bridge the gap between patients and physicians during the Coronavirus pandemic when social distancing was a preventive measure against the dreaded virus. Another remarkable fact about telemedicine is that it does not run solely on technology alone. In essence, it is the people using it that make

it relevant and impactful. This implies that if the patients are technophobic and the doctors are unwilling to use telemedicine as a tool, the whole idea of healing from a distance becomes unrealistic.

After the Asian continent, the world's second-largest and most populated continent is Africa, with about fifty-four countries. But despite the enormous human resources, mineral (metals and oil) endowment, and huge patronage from foreign companies who came on a mining spree. Africa has drawn little benefits from these mineral mining deals because it succumbed to resource mismanagement and parasitic neo-colonial relationships that undermined its productive capacity, making it one of the poorest continents on the globe. It is invariably saddening that almost fifty per cent of the African population is living in sheer penury. Due to the negative impacts of poverty, of which have a devastating impact on human psychology and physiology, Africa is by far the continent with the lowest life expectancy. As of 2017, the life expectancy at birth in Sub Saharan Africa was 63.9 years, and the healthy life expectancy (HALE) was only 55.2 years.

This implies that about 13.6% of one's lifetime is spent in poor health conditions, which is further elevated by the existing poor healthcare delivery. Healthcare delivery in Africa has been impeded by deficiencies and irregularities in social institutions, human resources, financial, technical and political developments. Ethnic warfare and disunity have continued to ruin Africa's socio-economic development.

Figure 1- This graph shows the average life expectancies around the world (Source: AP Environmental Science).

The decay of the healthcare sector in Africa has fuelled medical tourism and brain drain. As both patients, doctors, and other healthcare workers travel from Africa to Europe, Middle East, and America in droves for either medical treatment, better jobs, education and living; while leaving the poor masses who cannot afford a visa to uncertain fates. The persistence of healthcare workers industrial actions (strikes), poor resource allocation to the health sector, inadequate human resources, poor maintenance of existing infrastructure, corruption etc, has prevented optimal healthcare delivery in both urban, rural, and remote areas in Africa. All of these have further made the physician density in Africa very poor. Unbelievable as it may sound; thirty-one out of fifty-four countries in Africa have a doctor to patient ratio of about 1:10, 000; and the ratio of nurses and midwives to inhabitants is often nothing to write home about. The lack of healthcare professionals makes adequate healthcare

delivery almost a mirage. This underscores the failure of conventional face-to-face medicine in Africa.

However, to ensure public health and promote individual well-being amidst these unprecedented events, a telemedicine approach needs to be adopted and scaled-up in every part of the African continent (the conglomerate of developing countries). The emergence of telemedicine would be of great help to individuals living in remote areas that are characterized by poverty, bad roads, high dependency ratio, lack of physical infrastructure, enormous traditional healers and lack of orthodox healthcare workers etc. In these remote areas, people travel miles away to access basic amenities and may embark on a few days trip to obtain simple medical assistance from a faraway healthcare centre, when medical issues arise. These patients are predisposed to bad roads and high transport expenses. Unfortunately, the patients may die on the way, be predisposed to vehicular accidents due to bad roads, incur additional expenses from feeding and transport of escorting relatives who follow them to the hospital, and other unpredictable predicaments.

The remote areas in Africa are devoid of expected civilization. Thus, every

opportunity of improving healthcare delivery in these areas must not be left untapped. It would be wrong to shy away from telemedicine when it is obvious that there would never be enough brick and mortar hospitals and doctors. At this juncture, it would be necessary to analyze how telemedicine can invade Africa. Firstly, telemedicine should be taught as a course in the curriculum of African universities. Especially for those in the medical, paramedical, biomedical engineering fields of study. Medical students should take a rotation in telemedicine. For example on the 25th of February 2020, the clinical students of the College of Medicine and Health Sciences Abia State University Aba - Nigeria, were taught about telemedicine and its relevance. This knowledge intercourse would birth graduates (scientists, engineers, medical professionals) that understand the predicaments of healthcare delivery in Africa, and are willing to apply the idea of telemedicine. They would collaborate in the future to build teleconsultation centres and telemedicine systems that can run on low bandwidth because remote places in Africa often have weak internet bandwidth. As at 2011, the telemedicine program began in Amansie West District of Ghana, courtesy of the Novartis Foundation. Healthcare workers at these teleconsultation centres coach community health workers on how to manage emergency cases using telemedicine devices that include mobile phones, cameras, and computers with telemedicine software installed; thereby, avoiding unnecessary referrals of patients in remotes areas.

Figure 2 - The Teleconsultation machine at the College of Medicine and Health Sciences Abia State University, Aba - Nigeria

In Nigeria, the MobiHealth International founded by Dr Funmi Adewara a Nigerian doctor based in the UK, is innovative telemedicine and digital healthcare platform with a mission to bring affordable healthcare to underserved communities in Africa. Also, the eDoctor is a pan-African telemedicine platform offering online video medical consultations, to bridge the barriers of distance and time; their headquarters is at Bamenda, Cameroon. Ashrafcom is the leading provider of ICT and telemedicine services in the capital of Sudan, Khartoum. The Fundamental of Modern Telemedicine for Africa (FOMTA), Pan-African e- network project, Reseau en Afrique Francophone pour la Telemedicine (RAFT), are other telemedicine projects present in Sub Saharan Africa. All these telemedicine platforms have served as a stepping stone for telemedicine in Africa.

Secondly, the governments of each African country have a huge role to play. They are expected to make adequate allocations in the national budget for the health sector. They should make basic amenities, including, good hospitals, schools, constant electricity, good

roads, strong cellular network and high-speed internet available to the people. The government should promote and build ICT institutions, and combat inconstant power supply by harnessing solar energy in every corner of their nation, to prevent a digital divide. The government can devise means to attract health workers to isolated locations, by increasing the number of medical and paramedical students from remote areas, and also increasing the financial incentives of remote healthcare practice to prevent health inequalities. The ministry of health in various African countries is expected to set up many affordable or free teleconsultation centres across the country, with emphasis in the remote areas. A telemedicine regulatory body should be created by the government to create laws binding on telemedicine practice and ensuring the security of a patient's medical information. Finally, the government should create health insurance schemes that cover the field of telemedicine and ensure that healthcare workers who attend to patients via telemedicine are well paid. In addition to the expected roles of the government, various affluent individuals, Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and humanitarian aid agencies should include telemedicine as a tool for the achievement of their humanitarian objectives.

Once the art of telemedicine has invaded the consciousness of Africans, its presence

would be the key to unlock the padlocks of improved health care delivery in underserved remote places in Africa. The presence of telemedicine would revolutionize the health sector and increase the healthy life

expectancy (HALE) of Africans in so many ways that are worthy of examining.

Firstly, telemedicine would bridge the gap between African and foreign medics. The 24hours teleconsultation would help unravel the pathogenesis of complex diseases, reduce the possibility of attacks by aggrieved family members who are calmed by the overwhelming inputs of various specialists, and erase doubts in remote areas healthcare physicians as they become absolved of professional isolation, and are fortified to work more confidently amid limited resources at disposal. Secondly, telemedicine would be of clinical relevance by bringing affordable and quality healthcare to the remote areas. There would be no unnecessary referrals and patients won't have to travel long distances because the solutions of specialists come to their doorsteps. Unnecessary stress that arises from distant travels and long queues at hospitals would be minimized. Also, patients will be forced to stop using internet services like Google as a self-diagnostic tool, thereby protecting the patients from medical terminologies that can freak them out. Thus, patient mortality and morbidity rates would reduce drastically.

Thirdly, telemedicine would be of educational relevance because its foundation is based on learning from superiors (consultants) via lectures and workshops that occur through video and teleconferencing. This form of training (apprenticeship) will speed up the capacity and clinical skills of doctors and other healthcare workers in remote places. Making access to healthcare delivery in remote places a great possibility. Lastly, telemedicine can offer administrative benefits to healthcare workers in remote areas. Because it brings about collaboration amid health workers as operation-related information is transmitted fast and easy. Medical professionals in the remote areas can also be interviewed easily and promoted for higher incentives, instead of asking them to travel long distances and leaving their patients unattended.

In conclusion, telemedicine is the bedrock of efficient healthcare delivery across remote areas in Africa. It is an exciting area to watch for experimentation and new developments. It brings hope to the hopeless, becomes a classroom for healthcare workers, and acts as a saviour to the underserved people dwelling in remote areas. However, telemedicine is being hindered and made unpopular by several factors such as poor internet connection, illiteracy, unavailable basic amenities (e.g. electricity), poor affordability etc. The onus lies on the government, affluent individuals, NGOs, humanitarian agencies dwelling in Africa and overseas to rise to the occasion to make Africa porous to telemedicine, by the adoption of supportive measures that promote the viability of telemedicine in Africa. Telemedicine has proven to be an ornament in prosperity and a refuge in adversity; in fact, it is the highly promising future of efficient healthcare delivery across every remote area in Africa.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adam, W. D. and Margaret, A. C. (2000). *Telemedicine and Telehealth: Principles, Policies, Performances, and Pitfalls*. New York: Springer.

AP Environmental Science. (no date). *Life expectancy*. Available at:

<https://www.pinterest.com/pin/474003929501213441/> (Accessed 10 November 2020).

Aronson, S. H. (1977). „The Lancet on the telephone 1876-1975“, *Medical history*, 21(1), pp. 69–87. doi:10.1017/s0025727300037182.

Dasgupta, A. and Deb, S. (2008). „Telemedicine: a new horizon in public health in India“, *Indian journal of community medicine: official publication of Indian Association of Preventive & Social Medicine*, 33(1), 3–8. doi:10.4103/0970-0218.39234

- Doctors without Borders. (2020). *Telemedicine in Africa*. Available at: <https://www.doctorswithoutborders.ca/telemedicine> (Accessed: 11 November 2020)
- Fejro, C. N. Utibe, E. and Nchiewe, A. (2020). „Challenges and opportunities for telemedicine in Africa“, *Mail & Guardian*, 28 July. Available at: <https://mg.co.za/africa/2020-07-28-challenges-and-opportunities-for-telemedicine-in-africa/> (Accessed: 9 November 2020).
- Halit, E. and John, G. W. (2016). *Telemedicine and Electronic Medicine*. United States: CRC Press.
- Kenneth, B. D et al. (2020). „Telemedicine: an imperative concept during COVID-19 pandemic in Africa“, *Pan Africa Medical Journal*, 35(2), pp. 1-4. Available at: <https://www.panafrican-med-journal.com/content/series/35/2/129/full/> (Accessed: 9 November 2020).
- Michael, E. D. (1995). „Telemedicine has now come of age“, *Telemedicine Journal*. 1(1), pp. 3-4. Available at: <https://www.hon.ch/Library/papers/debakey.html> (Accessed: 10 November 2020).
- Oleribe, O.O. et al. (2019). „Identifying Key Challenges Facing Healthcare Systems in Africa and Potential Solutions“, *Dove Press journal: International Journal of General Medicine*. 12(1), pp. 395-403. Available at: <https://www.dovepress.com/identifying-key-challenges-facing-healthcare-systems-in-africa-and-pot-peer-reviewed-fulltext-article-IJGM> (Accessed: 13 November 2020).
- Said, B. Adnane, B. Smael, L. and Mustapha, H. (2016). „A Historic Case of Cardiac Surgery in Pregnancy“, *Hindawi Publishing Corporation*, 1(1), pp. 1-4. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/7518697> (Accessed: 10 November 2020).

- Saka, O. (2020). „Africa Needs Telemedicine to Overcome its Healthcare Challenges“, *Space in Africa*, 16 September. Available at: <https://africanews.space/africa-needs-telemedicine-to-overcome-its-medical-challenges/> (Accessed: 12 November 2020).
- Wamala, D. S. and Augustine, K. (2013). „A meta-analysis of telemedicine success in Africa“, *Journal of Pathology Informatics*, 4(6), pp. 1-5. Available at: <http://www.jpathinformatics.org/text.asp?2013/4/1/6/112686> (Accessed: 11 November 2020).
- Wikipedia. (no date). *Rural health*. Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rural_health (Accessed: 9 November 2020).
- Wikipedia. (no date). *Telehealth*. Available at: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Telehealth> (Accessed: 10 November 2020).
- World Health Organization. (2009). *Telemedicine Opportunities and Developments in Member States*. Available at: http://www.who.int/geo/publications/geo_telemedicine_2010.pdf (Accessed: 7 November 2020).